

Use of slow-release fertilizers to reduce nitrification

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Rice land soils in Orissa are alternately submerged and drained, which encourages nitrification of applied fertilizers and

reduces to 30% crop recovery of fertilizer nitrogen. We studied the effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on Ratna growth and yield at Bhubaneswar.

Soil was a sandy loam with pH 5.4 and 756.4 kg N, 26.5 kg P, and 181.4 kg K/ha. Nitrogen was applied as isobutylidene diurea (BDU), AM fertilizer, lac-coated urea, and as urea mixed with karanj cake (*Pongamia pinnata*), a local-

ly available, low-cost forest product suitable for mechanical blending with urea. Karanj contains 4% N, 0.79% P, and 1.3% K and retards nitrification.

The number of effective tillers per hill indicated the beneficial effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers (see table). Applying 100 kg N/ha as lac-coated urea or karanj cake-coated urea produced almost as many effective tillers/hill as 100 kg urea N/ha.

Maximum plant height was produced with karanj cake-coated urea, closely followed by lac-coated urea and 16-10-14 IBDU (see table).

Panicle length was greater for all slow-release nitrogen fertilizers at 100 kg N/ha. As urea application without slow-release treatment decreased, average panicle length declined. The control treatment had shortest panicles.

Lac-coated urea produced best grain filling and highest weight, followed by karanj cake-coated urea.

Lac-coated urea produced maximum grain yield of 5.1 t/ha, followed closely by karanj cake-coated urea. Nitrogen at 100 kg/ha applied as lac-coated or karanj cake-coated urea produced significantly better rice growth and yield than 200 kg N/ha applied as ordinary urea. □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers and urea on rice growth and yield, Bhubaneswar, India. ^a

Treatment	Growth attributes		Yield attributes			Grain yield (t/ha)
	Tillers/hill	Height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	1000-grain wt (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	
Urea 50 kg N/ha	6	62	20	27	56	3.1
Urea 100 kg N/ha	7	63	21	28	61	3.9
Urea 150 kg N/ha	7	64	22	28	65	4.2
Urea 200 kg N/ha	7	65	23	28	69	4.7
Sulfur-coated urea (S ₁) (100 kg N/ha)	8	65	24	29	70	4.8
Sulfur-coated urea (S ₂) (100 kg N/ha)	7	64	23	28	69	4.7
IBDU (10-10-10) (100 kg N/ha)	7	65	24	29	70	4.9
IBDU (16-10-14) (100 kg N/ha)	8	69	24	29	70	4.9
Lac-coated urea (100 kg N/ha)	8	70	25	29	72	5.0
AM (100 kg N/ha)	7	65	29	28	69	4.9
Karanj (100 kg N/ha)	8	70	24	29	71	5.1
Control	5	52	19	22	55	3.1
CD (0.05)	0.99	2.46	0.70	1.46	2.31	0.15

^aAll treatments received a basal application of 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha.

Effect of blue-green algae and nitrogen levels on rice yields

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We conducted multilocation experiments to determine the effect of blue-green algae (BGA) inoculation on rice yields in sandy to clay loam soils in Chhatis-

garh, Madhya Pradesh. Soil pH and available P at different locations are given in Table 1.

BGA was applied alone and in combination with nitrogen fertilizer, and 18 kg P and 12 kg K/ha were applied to all treat-

ments. Kranti, a medium-duration cultivar, was transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing. The crop was affected by grasshopper *Hieroglyphus banian* and bacterial blight, and pest control practices were used.

Table 1. Soil pH and available P of experimental soils.

Location	Soil type	Soil pH	Available P (kg/ha)
1981			
Regza	Sandy loam	7.6	16.6
Khoksa	Clay loam	7.8	15.9
Sarkanda	Clay loam	7.4	27.2
1982			
Sarkanda	Clay loam	1.5	15.4

Table 2. Average grain yield of rice as affected by blue-green algae and nitrogen levels.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1981			1982
	Regza (sandy loam)	Khoksa (clay loam)	Sarkanda (clay loam)	Sarkanda (clay loam)
Control (no BGA, no fertilizer)	3.0	1.7	2.3	3.9
10 BGA	3.4	2.0	2.7	4.6
20 N	3.3	2.7	3.7	5.2
20 N + 10 BGA	3.7	2.8	3.0	5.9
40 N	3.8	2.6	3.2	5.5
40 N + 10 BGA	3.8	2.8	3.5	6.2
60 N	3.9	2.6	3.9	6.2
60 N + 10 BGA	3.9	2.9	3.9	6.5
CD (0.005)	0.4	0.6	0.3	1.2

Application of 10 kg BGA/ha significantly increased the 1981 rice yield over the no-fertilizer, no-BGA control at the Government Farm in Regza and Sar-

kanda Bilaspur (Table 2). Combining 20 kg N and 10 kg BGA/ha caused a significant yield increase over 20 kg N/ha alone at Regza.

BGA did not develop spontaneously in the experimental fields. Scanty green algae biomass was noticed on N-fertilized plots. □

Optimum transplanting time for rice: an agrometeorological approach

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To maximize rice grain yield, it is necessary to determine optimum planting date. We used grain yield pattern and water and energy use efficiencies to determine correct planting date.

Our experiment at Raipur (21°14'N, 81°39'E) in the 1981 monsoon season was on clay loam with pH 6.5. Asha (R-35-2752), a dwarf indica, was planted in 3 replications at 10- × 20-cm spacing on 10 dates at 10-day intervals between 1 Jun and 30 Aug. Fertilizer was applied at 100 kg N, 26 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha. Net radiation and potential evapotranspiration values were estimated by Penman's equation and meteorological parameters recorded at the Agricultural Meteorology Observatory.

Phenological data, grain yield, yield-contributing characters, and total dry matter production are shown in the table. Yield-contributing characters varied little among transplanting dates, but there was a marked difference in grain yield pattern (see figure). Yield pattern and duration from sowing to 50% flowering indicated that transplanting between 11 and 21 Jul will produce optimum yields.

Water use efficiency (kg/ha per mm of

evapotranspiration) for grain yield was highest for rice transplanted between 11 and 31 Jul (see table). Water use efficiency for dry matter production was highest between 11 and 21 Jul.

Energy use efficiency did not vary significantly, but a definite relation existed between net accumulated radiation from flowering to maturity and grain yield pattern. Higher radiation produced higher yields. □

Accumulated evapotranspiration during different physiological stages, yield contributing characters, and water use efficiency of rice crops.

Transplanting date	Accumulated evapotranspiration (mm)			Total	Effective tillers/hill	Sound grains /panicle	Dry matter (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency for	
	Sowing to planting	Planting to 50% flowering	50% flowering to maturity						Grain yield (kg/ha per mm)	Dry matter (kg/ha per mm)
1.6.81	206	349	82	641	6.9	82	11.5	2.7	4.2	17.9
11.6.81	221	310	86	614	7.2	82	13.3	2.6	4.2	21.6
21.6.81	225	270	92	587	6.6	81	13.4	3.0	5.0	22.9
1.7.81	176	258	98	532	7.2	83	13.3	3.4	6.5	25.1
11.7.81	139	244	115	500	7.6	92	11.9	3.8	7.6	25.5
21.7.81	99	250	119	468	7.9	94	12.6	4.0	8.6	26.9
31.7.81	108	252	130	489	6.9	92	9.8	3.8	7.7	20.0
10.8.81	98	267	107	472	5.6	88	8.0	3.5	7.3	16.9
20.8.81	106	250	97	453	5.4	68	7.4	3.1	6.9	16.3
30.8.81	107	229	86	422	4.4	59	7.0	3.1	7.3	16.6

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